

Gender Discrimination in Educational and Social Sectors: A Case Study of Baluchistan

Author's Details:

¹Shahida Habib, ²Noor Ahmed Rodini, ³Abdullah Dostain, and ⁴Ahmed Ali Mengal ⁵Shazia Jaffer

¹Gender Studies Development University of Balochistan Quetta, Pakistan ²Pakistan Study Centre University of Balochistan Quetta, Pakistan- ³Livestock and Dairy Development Department Balochistan, Pakistan - ⁴Agribusiness Directorate, Agriculture Research Institute (ARI) Balochistan Quetta, Pakistan ⁵Pakistan Study Centre University of Balochistan Quetta, Pakistan

Corresponding Author: **Abdullah Dostain**

Abstract

The present research was aimed to explore the respondent's perception about gender discrimination in educational and social sectors. A sample size of 100 respondents from Balochistan province and each 25 from Quetta, Loralai, Matung and Ziarat districts of Balochistan province were selected by using sampling technique. SPSS was used for data analysis. The result reveals that most respondents fell in age category 31 to 40 (35%), most of the respondents were illiterate (53%). Non-significant differences were observed between the perceptions of the respondents at 0.01 alpha level regarding diverse items 2 out of 5 categories. Alike significant differences were also observed between the perceptions of the respondents on 3 out of 5 categories about the social aspect. Following recommendation put forward. Female is the foremost and indispensable division in development ladder. Therefore it should be suggested that free of cost education (primary to graduate schooling) scheme and social development program should be started in order to accelerate the female educational and social directions and obtained the Million Development Goals about female empowerment.

Keywords: discrimination, gender, education, Baluchistan

Introduction

Educational and social development aspects play an imperative and essential role in all direction of life. The development of female with the term of social and education practices has led to a worldwide discussion of how to convey an equal education opportunity for all without any sort of discrimination. The female in society and higher education is left behind in spite of the fact that it is most effective and smart investment for economic growth of and development of any country around the globe.

Regardless of the global expansion of higher education and social dimensions' duration, the 21st century were still a rigid mission, in this connection, the inequalities of entry persist just about far and wide. discrimination by gender is the handicap aspects of development and non-development countries. As a result, the development process with a term of gender procedure or expansion was still restricted either financial, socially or cultural. All these development or massive motives and various combinations, reveals the perpetuate uncertainty (UNDP, 2003). Discrimination toward females used to be nonetheless familiar in society including in the present labor market provisions for females (Rees, 1990). However, in this regard, career progression and an inequality of pay, the perspective in the direction of childcare, the ideology of gender equality and the existence, and they have an impact on of gender equality legislation (Rees, 1990). From that perspective the educational and social system that lead opinion in society, gender-related discrimination toward females and employees. Female scholars faced ordinary access problems such as perceived stereotypes and an absence of confident role models in all areas of their graduate careers. These included application strategies, evaluation, and absence of a flexible entry. Globally, females staff members had faced different discrimination. Not only was this inherently damaging the careers and determinations of those females, but also had faced a negative impact on educationally or socially.

Problem statement

Gender aspect in development countries play a massive and starring role in development process. Balochistan province is considered as the largest province of the country, but poorer physical infrastructure. For females, there is no equal occasion in social and educational aspects at province level. Due to its tribal and male dominate society the female as regarded as the oppressed classes in province society. As a result, the accesses of a female in educational and social aspects did not achieve their desired goals. There is a dire need for policymakers to focus the social and educational need for women and women empowerment. Thus, the present study was indicating that discrepancy in a social and educational

circle with their term of gender development, so that catered the difficulties in getting social and education cause of gender discrimination.

Objectives

1. To explore the socio-economic profile of respondents.
2. To determine the social and education dimensions and needs of respondents.
3. To develop the firm suggestions for policymakers.

Methodology

Researchers design in the current study was used a descriptive type of survey method, because the descriptive method was most suitable to acquiring the person’s perception snapshot on social facts and figure (Gall et al., 2007; Trochim 2000) and is measured as a correct methods to determine the socio-economic evidence on existing condition (Cohen et al., 2007). The sample size and target population of the current research were comprised of respondents as beneficiaries. A sample size of 100 respondents from Balochistan province and each 25 from Quetta, Loralai, Matung and Ziarat districts of Balochistan province were selected by using the non-probability sampling technique i.e. convenience sampling, where the subjects are carefully chosen on account of their convenient approachability and proximity to the researcher (Saunders et al., 2012). The sample size of respondents was determined by using (McCall 1980) table of “selecting sample sizes” at the 0.01 percent error rate. A comprehensive opinion poll as research instrument was settled keeping in view the objectives of the current research. In the current research, the Liker scaling was used for rating of attitude on 5-point scales so as to discover the perception of the respondents (Likert 1932). Cronbach’s Alpha program was rummage-sale in order to test the reliability of the questionnaire used in present research (Aryet al., 1996). The reliability coefficients ranged from .852 to .743 demonstrating that the internal consistency of the research instrument was good (Nunnally). Henceforth; the raw data was tabularized and set out for analyzed by quantitative and standard statistical techniques, with the assistant of Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) and Excel, 2016. A Least Significant Difference (LSD) was made between items about diverse variables by using One-Way ANOVA (analysis of variance).

Results and discussions

Age composition was considered as the imperative variable and most important socio-economic evidence as shown in figure-1.

Figure-1 Age of the respondents.

In this regard, the results of figure-1 depict that most of the respondents were fall in the age category 31 to 40 (35%), followed by 23% of the respondents were fall in 21 to 30 year. While most 17-14% of the respondents fell in age categories of 41 to 50 and above 50 respectively.

The main theme of education was bringing about the desired changes in human behavior. Educational aspects not only alteration the attitude of the human being but also reflect the positive impact on motivational length of the individuals. In this regard, the education level was categories into seven categories.

Figure-2 Educational level of the respondents.

The results of figure-2 reveal that most of the respondents were illiterate (53%) followed by 18% of the respondents holds matriculation certificate, and 9% of the respondents having a primary certificate.

Table-1: Comparison between respondent’s perception about educational circle

Categories	Items				MS	f-value	Sig*
	Male		Female				
	M	SD	M	SD			
Access to basic education	3.65	.903	4.17	.592	.710	8.673	.004*
Literacy rate for female	3.39	1.024	3.83	.834	.968	4.684	.032
Improve advocacy for female	2.64	1.097	3.20	1.095	1.202	6.021	.015*
Educational and economic productivity	3.92	.981	4.20	.610	.829	2.181	.142
Decision-making and empowerment	3.42	1.065	2.40	1.133	1.168	20.548	.000*

Scale 1 = Strongly disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Undecided, 4= Agree, 5= Strongly agree

* Significant at 0.01 Level

The respondents were asked to acknowledge their perceptions regarding diverse items on 5 points Likert scale. Table-1 depicts the result. Means for groups in homogeneous subset were significant: access to basic education (F= 8.673; P.01);

improve advocacy for female (F= 6.021; P.01) and decision-making and empowerment (F= 20.548; P.01); respectively. Non-significant differences were observed between the perceptions of the respondents at 0.01 alpha level regarding diverse items 2 out of 5. It was concluded that restriction still existed in educational as aspect for female.

Table-2: Comparison between respondent’s perception about social aspects

Categories	Items				MS	f-value	Sig*
	Male		Female				
	M	SD	M	SD			
Social norm restriction	3.37	1.134	2.40	1.133	1.285	16.894	.000*
Gender division of labor	3.52	1.010	3.27	1.081	1.053	1.406	.238
Household Convenience	3.49	.904	3.50	.861	.801	.003	.957
Societal support for learning	3.43	.998	3.53	.973	.984	.250	.618
Political empowerment	3.86	.876	2.97	1.189	.914	20.147	.000*

Scale 1 = Strongly disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Undecided, 4= Agree, 5= Strongly agree

* Significant at 0.01 Level

Table-2 results represent that there was variation in the perceptions of respondents occurred at 0.01 level. Means for groups in homogeneous subset were highly significant at 0.01 level: social norm restriction (F= 16.894; P.01); and political empowerment (F= 20.147; P.01); respectively. Non-significant differences were also observed between the perceptions of the respondents on diverse items from 3 out of 5 categories. It was concluded that constraints regarding social dimension still existed.

Conclusion and recommendations

The research survey information presented that overall educational and social aspects of the female are not encouraging and positive ways. Nevertheless, the concerns raised regarding the educational trends, and social aspects gap is still happened, to doing so, it is dire need to address these issues at a greater extent so that to achieve the desired outcome with the term of gender discrimination and comprehend the realities and intricacies of these concerns. Following recommendation put forward. Female is the foremost and indispensable division in development ladder. Therefore it should be suggested that free of cost education (primary to graduate schooling) scheme and social development program should be started in order to accelerate the female educational and social directions and obtained the Million Development Goals about female empowerment.

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